

A

A

A

A

Amino Acid
Position

I Y K
162 163 164
G C C A T C T A C

TP53^{+/+}

Amino Acid
Position

I C A
162 163 164
G C C A T C T G C

TP53^{-/-}
Clone 1

TP53^{-/-}
Clone 2
Allele 1

Amino Acid
Position

I S Q
162 163 164
G C C A T C T C T

TP53^{-/-}
Clone 2
Allele 2

